

THE IMPORTANCE OF PEDAGOGICAL TECHNOLOGIES IN CURRENT HISTORY LESSONS AND THEIR APPLICATION IN THE LESSON

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Annotation: *At a time when production technologies are developing rapidly, the field of education, like other industrial institutions, prepares competitive, knowledgeable, educated people for the development of the Motherland, using scientific, based new pedagogical technologies, information and qualified specialists. developing as an industry.*

Keywords: *pedagogy, technology, development, information*

INTRODUCTION Today's rapidly changing economic, social and spiritual life requires the widespread use of new pedagogical interactive methods in shaping the worldview of young learners. 'The traditional lesson is releasing transition forms.

The use of modern pedagogical technologies in the educational process requires, first of all, the humanization of pedagogical relations. Because any technology used without it does not give the expected effect.

The constant optimization of the educational process depends on the use of new and improving pedagogical technologies in the teaching process in different directions and purposes.

The main goal of any pedagogical technology is to identify the ways to achieve the end result and to achieve it without fail.

LITERATURE ANALYSIS AND METHODOLOGY

We believe that the most basic principle of pedagogical technology is that it depends on the technology chosen by the teacher and the student to achieve a guaranteed result from the set goal, that is, in the teaching process, to achieve a guaranteed result on the goal. If each educational technology used can create a collaborative activity between teacher and student, if both can achieve a positive result, if students can think independently, work creatively, explore in the learning process, if they can analyze, if they can draw their own conclusions, if they can evaluate themselves, the group, and the group, and the teacher can create opportunities and conditions for such activities, in our opinion, this is the basis of the teaching process.

Each lesson, topic, subject has its own technology, that is, pedagogical technology in the learning process is an individual process, which is based on the needs of the student. 'nalted. is a pedagogical process designed to produce pre-designed and guaranteed results.

Therefore, every educator should set a goal before passing their lessons. After all, this future generation must grow up harmoniously, which will contribute to the development of our country. The task of every science teacher is to educate the harmoniously developed generation in a meaningful way.

The role of such pedagogical technologies in history lessons is also invaluable. It is not possible to ask each student the topic in 45 minutes. In doing so, we can use a variety of methods to find out how well the reader understands the topic. To do this, we can choose this pedagogical technology or method in our lesson, taking into account the topic, the age of the student. In history lessons, the student is required to memorize the names, dates, and historical terms of more historical figures, and we need to pay special attention to these in each topic.

RESULTS

Description of educational technologies

BBB technology

(I know, I want to know, I know)

Coverage of the administrative-military structure of the Amur Temur Kingdom using BBB technology. Students are divided into groups. The teacher asks the students what they know about Amir Temur and writes the students' answers in the I know column.

In the second column he writes what he wants to know about A. Temur.

In the third column, students write down what they have learned.

I know	I want to know	I found out
1. Amir Temur was born on April 9, 1336	How did Amir Temur rule the country?	The administration consists of two departments, a dargah and a ministry
2. The year 1365 was the Battle of Mud	To whom did Amir Temur divide the state?	He took his land to his relatives
3. Amir Temur wrote the rules of Temur	What was the military art of Amir Temur?	Amir Temur's army was formed on the basis of 10 military units
4. In 1370, Amir Temur established a centralized state in Movaraunnahr	What kind of book are Temur's rules?	Timur's statutes are a historical legal book

DISCUSSION

Category table technology

This method is much simpler than other methods and is easy for students to use in class. This method is able to include the question, topic problem or historical figures, terms, chronological information and allows the student to think independently and choose alternative ideas and answers. This is exactly what it is for the convenience of the reader.

Coverage of the topic "Genghis Khan's invasion" using category table technology.

The Mongol state	Chronological category	Which country do you belong to	Origin
Genghis Khan	1206.	The Mongol state	Qiyat seed
Joji	1219.	Signal	The seed of Genghis Khan
Chigatoy	20s of the XIII century	Movarounnahr, East Turkestan	The seed of Genghis Khan
Oktoy	1227.	Blackbird	The seed of Genghis Khan

"Resume technology"

This technology is complex, multidisciplinary, and provides information on a variety of topics. For example, the pros and cons, advantages and disadvantages, advantages and disadvantages are identified. It teaches students to think freely, independently, critically, to work as a team, to summarize and compare ideas, to express their opinions independently, to apply the knowledge they have acquired from the topics covered. This technology can be used in seminars, practical classes, individually or in small groups, as well as in homework assignments.

Categorical table on "Pre-Asian countries and their neighbors" using "resume" technology.

Assyria		Hittite and		Urartu	
Achievements	Problems	Achievements	Problems	Achievements	Problems
BC XX state was formed. Mil.avv. It flourished in the 13th century	The warring people were constantly at war with the neighboring countries.	Mil.avv. Founded in the XVIII century. The capital is	Occupied Syrian cities. Babylon was plundered.	Located behind the Caucasus. It flourished during the reign of Sardur I	He carried out raids. He left the stage of history in 590 BC.

Conclusion

CONCLUSION

The technologies mentioned in the article are the technologies used in history lessons in schools, which play a key role in helping students to study the history of the ancient world and the history of medieval Uzbekistan and the world. It is recommended that similar technologies be applied to other subjects of science as well.

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